

ROLE OF YOGA IN STRESS REDUCTION - A CLINICAL STUDY

*DR. AMRUTHA MANOHARAN, BHMS, MD (Hom.), DIPLOMA IN YOGA
DIPLOMA IN CLINICAL COSMETOLOGY, PGDPHM,
MEDICAL OFFICER, NATIONAL AYUSH MISSION*

ABSTRACT

Stress is one of the normal, feelings each and every human being experiences. It is of two types. *Eustress* or good stress is the stress that benefits our health. *Distress* or bad stress is the stress that harms the health which often results from imbalances between needs and resources for dealing with those needs. may yoga asanas are available for reducing stress. ⁽¹⁾

INTRODUCTION

Yoga is the most ancient system of medicine practiced. Which consists of a group of physical, mental, and spiritual practices. Stressful life events are shown to provoke a sequence of psychological and physiological adjustments including nervous, endocrine, and immune mechanisms. ⁽²⁾

Yoga plays a beneficial role in managing stress-related mental illnesses like stress, depression and anxiety. Yoga is mind-body medicine widely found to be beneficial in various psycho-somatic disorders. ⁽³⁾Yoga includes physical postures, breathing practices, meditation, and also moral principles (yama & niyama) which help in emotional culturing to reduce inner conflicts.

According to a recent review of yoga's effect on stress, a yoga intervention resulted in a significant reduction in stress. ⁽⁴⁾

The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is the most widely used psychological instrument for measuring the perception of stress.

► Scores ranging from 0-13 would be considered low stress. ► Scores ranging from 14-26 would be considered moderate stress. ► Scores ranging from 27-40 would be considered high perceived stress ⁽⁵⁾

METHODOLOGY

30 random cases with stress was selected from OPD and stress assessment was done with perceived stress scale PSS at the time of visit the patients were given an awareness about of yoga and surya namskra and balasana was thought. The patient was regularly asked to do this for 50 days and the perceived stress scale PSS was again done.

DISCUSSION

Yoga has a very marked improvement in reducing stress.

Marked improvement of stress level was observed in patients . 25 patients have marked relief of stress and pss score reduction and 5 persons have moderate relief of stress and pss symptom score.

Male 7, Female 23

PSS SCORE BEFORE YOGA	PSS SCORE AFTER YOGA
27 TO 40 , 24 CASES	0 TO 13 , 25 CASES
14 TO 26, 6 CASES	14 TO 26 , 5 CASES

CONCLUSION

Yoga has a very marked improvement in reducing stress. And improving the quality of life.

Marked improvement of stress level was observed in patients . 25 patients have marked relief of stress and pss score reduction and 5 persons have moderate relief of stress and pss symptom score.

REFERENCES

1. H. Selye Confusion and controversy in the stress field *Hum Stress*, 1 (2) (1975), pp. 37-44
2. L. Yang, Y. Zhao, Y. Wang, L. Liu, X. Zhang, B. Li, *et al.* The effects of psychological stress on depression *Curr Neuropharmacol*, 13 (4) (2015), pp. 494-504
3. Z.R. Mulla, V.R. Krishnan Karma-yoga: the Indian model of moral development *J Bus Ethics*, 123 (2) (2014), pp. 339-351
4. H. Cramer, R. Lauche, J. Langhorst, G. Dobos Yoga for depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis *Depress Anxiety*, 30 (11) (2013), pp. 1068-1083
5. Perceived Stress Scale